

ISic1103

I.Sicily inscription 1103

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Lost?

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Drepanum

Place of origin (modern)

Trapani

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Trapani

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1 : mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2 : mm

Text

Edition: EDR107959

1. [Γ(άιον) Ἀσίονιον]
2. [N]εικόμ [αχον]
3. [I]ουλιανὸ [v]
4. ὕπατον
5. Εὐτυχίω [v]
6. ἐπίτροπο[ς]

Edition: PHI140587

1. [Γ(άιον) Ἀσίονιον N]-
2. εικόμ[αχον Ἴ]-
3. ουλιανὸ [v]
4. ὕπατον
5. Εὐτυχίω [v]
6. ἐ[π]ίτροπο[ς].
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284998

EDR 107959

EDCS 39102261

PHI 140587

Bibliography

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